

Unitarity Enables Grokking: Entanglement Phase Transitions in Quantum Circuits on Modular Arithmetic

Liang Wang*

School of Artificial Intelligence and Automation
Huazhong University of Science and Technology
Wuhan 430070, P.R. China
wangliang.f@gmail.com

Abstract

Grokking—delayed generalization long after memorization—has been observed almost exclusively in classical networks trained with weight decay. We show that 9-layer parameterized quantum circuits (PQCs, 463 parameters) grok modular addition ($a+b \bmod 23$) *without* weight decay, achieving a 25% grok rate across 20 seeds. A classical transformer (14,304 parameters) requires weight decay ($\lambda=1.0$) for 100% grokking and fails without it. Weight decay has opposite effects on the two architectures: removing it improves quantum test accuracy (68.7% vs. 42.3%; Mann–Whitney $p=0.002$) while eliminating classical grokking entirely. Tracking the bipartite entanglement entropy (EE) of the circuit state, we find that successful grokking occurs in a sweet spot ($EE \in [3.1, 4.1]$), while EE overshoot above 4.2 triggers a “grok-then-ungrok” phenomenon—test accuracy rises to 93.7% then collapses to 11.3% as entanglement saturates. Ablations confirm that entanglement is necessary (product-state circuits reach $\sim 0.2\%$) and that PQCs are more parameter-efficient than size-matched classical models. These results connect quantum unitarity to implicit regularization and entanglement dynamics to generalization transitions.

Code and data: <https://github.com/maris205/quantum-grok>

1 Introduction

Grokking, the phenomenon in which a neural network first memorizes its training data and then—after a prolonged period of apparent stagnation—suddenly generalizes to held-out examples, was first reported by Power et al. (2022) on small algorithmic tasks including modular arithmetic. Since then, grokking has attracted significant interest as a window into how neural networks transition from memorization to generalization (Nanda et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023). A recurring theme in this literature is the central role of *explicit regularization*: weight decay appears necessary for classical models to escape the memorization regime and discover generalizing solutions (Theis, 2023).

In parallel, parameterized quantum circuits (PQCs) have emerged as a class of machine learning models with fundamentally different inductive biases from classical networks (Schuld and Killoran, 2019; Cerezo et al., 2021). PQCs are inherently unitary: each layer preserves the ℓ_2 norm of the quantum state. This norm preservation imposes a structural constraint that has no direct analog in standard classical architectures and raises a natural question: *can unitarity substitute for explicit regularization in enabling grokking?*

We present evidence in this direction. We train 9-layer PQCs with 463 parameters on the task $(a+b) \bmod 23$ and observe grokking *without any weight decay* in 5 of 20 random seeds. In contrast, classical transformers with 14,304 parameters require strong weight decay ($\lambda = 1.0$) to grok, and fail to generalize without it. The opposite effect of weight decay on the two architectures—beneficial for classical models, harmful for quantum circuits—suggests that the unitary structure of PQCs provides an implicit regularization that can serve a similar functional role to weight decay in classical training.

Beyond the existence of quantum grokking, we study its mechanism through the lens of entanglement. We track the bipartite entanglement entropy (EE) of the circuit’s quantum state during training and find that EE serves as a diagnostic for the generalization transition. Seeds that grok reach a “sweet spot” EE range of 3.1–4.1 at the grok step. Seeds whose

*Correspondence: wangliang.f@gmail.com

38 EE overshoots above 4.2 exhibit a striking *grok-then-ungrok* phenomenon: test accuracy rises sharply, then collapses as
 39 the circuit state becomes maximally entangled and loses its ability to encode useful structure. This observation connects
 40 grokking to entanglement phase transitions, extending recent tensor-network results (Wang et al., 2025) to gate-based
 41 quantum circuits on modular arithmetic.

42 Our contributions are:

- 43 1. **Quantum grokking without weight decay.** We demonstrate that 9-layer PQCs (463 parameters) grok modular
 44 addition with a 25% rate across 20 seeds (Section 4.2). Removing weight decay improves quantum test accuracy
 45 from 42.3% to 68.7% ($p = 0.002$), while eliminating classical grokking entirely (Section 4.3).
- 46 2. **Entanglement entropy as a grokking diagnostic.** We identify an EE sweet-spot ($EE \in [3.1, 4.1]$) that correlates
 47 with successful generalization and an overshoot regime ($EE > 4.2$) that triggers catastrophic forgetting (Section 4.4).
- 48 3. **Grok-then-ungrok phenomenon.** We report a case (seed 6) in which a circuit generalizes to 93.7% test accuracy
 49 then collapses to 11.3% as EE rises from 3.1 to 4.3—a new failure mode with a physically interpretable cause
 50 (Section 4.4).
- 51 4. **Ablations.** Product-state circuits (no entanglement) fail entirely ($\sim 0.2\%$ test), and parameter-matched classical
 52 models ($d=4$, 444 params) reach only $\sim 30\%$ training accuracy, confirming that entanglement is necessary and
 53 quantum circuits are more parameter-efficient (Section 4.5).

54 2 Background

55 **Grokking.** Grokking refers to delayed generalization: a model achieves near-perfect training accuracy early in
 56 optimization, yet test accuracy remains at chance for many additional steps before abruptly rising (Power et al., 2022).
 57 The canonical setting is modular arithmetic—learning $(a \circ b) \bmod p$ from a fraction of all p^2 input pairs. Nanda et al.
 58 (2023) showed that small transformers learn a Fourier multiplication algorithm for this task, with *weight decay* driving
 59 the memorization-to-generalization transition (Theis, 2023).

60 **Parameterized quantum circuits.** A parameterized quantum circuit (PQC) acts on n qubits initialized in $|0\rangle^{\otimes n}$,
 61 applying parameterized rotations (R_Y, R_Z) interleaved with fixed entangling gates (e.g., CZ). After L layers, Pauli- Z
 62 expectation values are measured and fed into a classical readout head (Cerezo et al., 2021). The circuit implements a
 63 unitary $U(\theta) \in \text{SU}(2^n)$; gradients are computed via adjoint differentiation (Jones and Julienne, 2020). A key property
 64 is that each layer preserves the ℓ_2 norm $\|\psi\| = 1$ exactly—an intrinsic constraint with no classical analog.

65 **Entanglement entropy.** Given a bipartite split of n qubits into subsystems A and B , the entanglement entropy (EE)
 66 of a pure state $|\psi\rangle$ is the von Neumann entropy of the reduced density matrix:

$$EE = S(\rho_A) = -\text{tr}(\rho_A \log_2 \rho_A), \quad \rho_A = \text{tr}_B |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|. \quad (1)$$

67 EE ranges from 0 (product state) to $n_A = |A|$ (maximally entangled) and serves as an order parameter for quantum phase
 68 transitions (Eisert et al., 2010). Wang et al. (2025) connected grokking in tensor-network models to an entanglement
 69 dynamical transition; we extend this to gate-based PQCs on modular arithmetic.

70 3 Method

71 We describe the quantum circuit architecture, the classical baselines, and the training protocol. All models are trained
 72 on the task $(a + b) \bmod 23$, where $a, b \in \{0, 1, \dots, 22\}$.

73 3.1 Binary Input Encoding

74 Each integer $a \in \{0, \dots, 22\}$ is encoded into $n_{\text{bits}} = \lceil \log_2 23 \rceil = 5$ binary digits. The two inputs (a, b) are concatenated
 75 into a 10-dimensional binary vector $\mathbf{x} \in \{0, 1\}^{10}$, which is loaded onto 10 qubits via trainable-angle encoding:

$$|\psi_0(\mathbf{x})\rangle = \bigotimes_{i=1}^{10} R_Y(x_i \cdot s_i)|0\rangle, \quad (2)$$

76 where s_i are learnable scaling parameters initialized to π . Qubits 1–5 encode a and qubits 6–10 encode b . Binary
77 encoding keeps the qubit count logarithmic in the modulus, allowing classical simulation of the full circuit.

78 3.2 CZ Entangling Circuit

79 The circuit consists of L layers, each containing parameterized single-qubit rotations followed by CZ entangling gates.
80 In each layer ℓ :

- 81 1. Apply $R_Y(\theta_{i,\ell})$ and $R_Z(\phi_{i,\ell})$ to each qubit $i \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$.
- 82 2. Apply CZ gates according to a fixed topology (described below).

83 After the final layer, one additional round of R_Y/R_Z rotations is applied without entangling gates.

84 **CZ topology.** Each layer applies 20 CZ gates: 10 inter-token gates connecting matching and shifted bit positions
85 between the two 5-qubit registers, and 10 intra-token gates forming a ring within each register (see Appendix D for the
86 complete gate list). This topology ensures all qubits can influence each other within a few layers.

87 **Parameter count.** Each layer contributes $10 \times 2 = 20$ rotation parameters, plus 10 input scaling parameters and one
88 final rotation round of 20 parameters. A circuit with L layers has $(L + 1) \times 20 + 10$ quantum parameters. Adding the
89 classical readout head (described below), a 9-layer circuit has 463 trainable parameters in total.

90 3.3 Classical Readout Head

91 After executing the circuit, we measure the Pauli- Z expectation values $\langle Z_i \rangle$ for all 10 qubits, producing a 10-dimensional
92 real vector $z \in [-1, 1]^{10}$. A trainable linear layer $W \in \mathbb{R}^{23 \times 10}$ (with bias) maps z to logits over the 23 output classes:

$$o = Wz + b, \quad \hat{y} = \arg \max_c o_c. \quad (3)$$

93 The readout head contributes $23 \times 10 + 23 = 253$ parameters.

94 3.4 Training Protocol

95 **Data split.** The full dataset consists of $23^2 = 529$ pairs (a, b) with labels $(a + b) \bmod 23$. We use a 70/30 train/test
96 split (370 training, 159 test examples), following the standard grokking setup (Power et al., 2022). The split is
97 randomized per seed.

98 **Optimization.** All quantum models are trained with AdamW (Loshchilov and Hutter, 2019) using learning rate
99 $\eta = 0.05$ and *no weight decay* ($\lambda = 0$). We use mini-batches of size 64, sampling without replacement from the training
100 set at each step. Gradients are computed via adjoint differentiation on the `lightning.qubit` backend of PennyLane
101 (Bergholm et al., 2018).

102 **Classical baselines.** The primary classical baseline is a 1-layer transformer with $d_{\text{model}} = 32$, 2 attention heads,
103 and causal masking, following the standard grokking architecture (Power et al., 2022; Nanda et al., 2023). Inputs are
104 tokenized as $(a, b, =)$ with learned token and positional embeddings. The classical model has 14,304 parameters and is
105 trained with AdamW ($\eta = 10^{-3}$, $\lambda = 1.0$, $\beta_2 = 0.98$) using full-batch gradient descent.

106 **Grokking criterion.** We define a model as having “grokked” if (i) its training accuracy has reached $\geq 99\%$ at some
107 earlier step, and (ii) its test accuracy subsequently exceeds 90%, consistent with the delayed-generalization definition of
108 Power et al. (2022). We additionally require that test accuracy remain above 50% at the grok step to filter transient
109 spikes. The “grok step” is the first training step satisfying these criteria.

Table 1: Model configurations. “Q” = quantum, “C” = classical transformer, “PS” = product state (no CZ gates). Parameter counts include all trainable parameters (quantum rotations, input scaling, and readout head for quantum models; all weights for classical models).

Model	Type	Layers	Params	LR	WD
Q-3L	PQC + CZ	3	343	0.05	0.0
Q-6L	PQC + CZ	6	403	0.05	0.0
Q-9L	PQC + CZ	9	463	0.05	0.0
Q-12L	PQC + CZ	12	523	0.05	0.0
PS-3L	PQC (no CZ)	3	343	0.05	0.0
C- d_{32}	Transformer	1	14,304	10^{-3}	1.0
C- d_4	Transformer	1	444	10^{-3}	1.0

Figure 1: Learning curves for modular arithmetic (mod-23). (a) A quantum circuit seed that groks: test accuracy rises sharply after prolonged memorization. (b) A quantum seed that does not grok: training accuracy saturates but test accuracy plateaus. (c) A classical 1-layer transformer with weight decay ($\lambda = 1.0$), showing characteristic delayed generalization. Dashed vertical lines mark the grok step.

3.5 Entanglement Entropy Tracking

We compute the bipartite EE (Eq. 1) every 500 steps during training, splitting the 10 qubits into the two 5-qubit input registers. For each measurement, we obtain the full statevector for 10 training inputs, compute ρ_A via partial trace, and average the von Neumann entropy. The maximum EE under this bipartition is 5 bits.

Table 1 summarizes the model configurations used in our experiments.

4 Experiments

4.1 Setup

All experiments use modular addition $(a + b) \bmod 23$ with a 70/30 train/test split (370/159 examples). Quantum circuits are simulated using PennyLane’s `lightning.qubit` backend with adjoint differentiation. Each quantum training step (forward + backward pass, batch of 64) takes approximately 1.1 seconds on a single CPU core. Unless otherwise noted, quantum models are trained for 50,000 steps and classical models for 30,000 steps. We define the *grok step* as the first step at which test accuracy exceeds 90%, with the additional requirement that test accuracy at that step is above 50% (to filter transient spikes).

4.2 Main Result: Quantum Grokking Without Weight Decay

Our primary finding is that 9-layer quantum circuits grok modular addition without weight decay. Figure 1 shows representative learning curves.

Table 2: Main results on $(a + b) \bmod 23$. Grok rate is the fraction of seeds achieving and sustaining test accuracy above 90%. Mean test accuracy is computed over all seeds at the final step. CI = 95% bootstrap confidence interval.

Model	WD	Params	Seeds	Grok rate	Mean test acc.	p -value
Q-9L	0.0	463	20	5/20 (25%)	$68.7 \pm 20.8\%$	—
Q-9L	0.1	463	10	0/10 (0%)	$42.3 \pm 15.1\%$	0.002 [†]
C- $d32$	1.0	14,304	5	5/5 (100%)	>99%	—
C- $d32$	0.0	14,304	3	0/3 (0%)	~4%	—

[†] Mann–Whitney U test, two-sided, comparing final test accuracy of Q-9L (no WD, $n = 20$) vs. Q-9L (WD = 0.1, $n = 10$).

Figure 2: Effect of weight decay on final test accuracy. Quantum circuits without weight decay achieve significantly higher test accuracy than with $WD = 0.1$ (Mann–Whitney $p = 0.002$). Classical transformers show the opposite pattern: $WD = 1.0$ is required for grokking. Horizontal bars indicate medians; individual seeds are shown as dots.

126 Out of 20 random seeds, 5 seeds (25%) achieve test accuracy above 90% that is sustained until the end of training—
 127 the standard grokking threshold. A sixth seed (seed 6) briefly crosses 90% before collapsing, a phenomenon we analyze
 128 in Section 4.4. The 95% bootstrap confidence interval for the grok rate is [10%, 50%]. In contrast, the classical
 129 transformer with weight decay ($\lambda = 1.0$) achieves a 100% grok rate (5/5 seeds). While the grok rate difference is not
 130 statistically significant by Fisher’s exact test ($p = 0.14$; see Appendix C), the qualitative difference in the *mechanism* is
 131 notable: the quantum circuit groks without any explicit regularization.

132 Table 2 summarizes the comparison; per-seed results are in Appendix B. The quantum model uses $30\times$ fewer
 133 parameters than the classical baseline and requires no weight decay. Classical models without weight decay fail to grok
 134 (0/3 seeds).

135 4.3 Weight Decay Ablation: Opposite Effects on Quantum and Classical

136 Weight decay has opposite effects on quantum and classical models. For quantum circuits, removing weight decay
 137 significantly improves test accuracy (Mann–Whitney U test, $p = 0.002$, comparing 20 no-WD seeds against 10
 138 $WD = 0.1$ seeds). For classical transformers, weight decay is essential: without it, the model memorizes perfectly but
 139 test accuracy never rises above chance.

140 Figure 2 shows the distribution of final test accuracy under all four conditions (quantum \pm WD, classical \pm WD).
 141 The quantum no-WD condition produces the highest-variance distribution, reflecting the stochastic nature of quantum
 142 grokking across seeds, but its median and mean are both significantly higher than the quantum with-WD condition.

143 This asymmetry has a natural interpretation. Classical networks have unconstrained weight norms: without weight
 144 decay, the optimization landscape allows the model to find sharp, memorizing solutions with arbitrarily large weights.

Figure 3: Entanglement entropy and generalization. **(a)** EE trajectories during training for seven tracked seeds. Solid lines: seeds that grok; dashed: non-grokking controls; dash-dotted: seed 6 (ungrok). Triangular markers indicate peak test accuracy. **(b)** EE at the grok step (or final EE for non-grok seeds) vs. final test accuracy. The blue band marks the sweet-spot EE range (3.1–4.1) associated with successful generalization.

145 Weight decay penalizes large norms, pushing the model toward flatter, generalizing solutions. Quantum circuits, by
 146 contrast, are unitary: the quantum state norm is exactly 1 at every layer, regardless of the rotation angles. Adding
 147 weight decay to a quantum circuit shrinks the rotation angles toward zero, making the circuit closer to the identity
 148 transformation—this reduces expressivity without providing the norm-control benefit that motivates weight decay in
 149 classical training.

150 4.4 Entanglement Entropy Dynamics

151 We track the bipartite entanglement entropy (EE) across training for seven seeds selected from the 9-layer no-WD
 152 experiments: three that grok and sustain it, two controls (no grok), one that exhibits the “grok-then-ungrok” phenomenon
 153 (seed 6), and one that approaches but does not reach the grok threshold.

154 **EE as a grokking diagnostic.** Figure 3(a) shows EE trajectories for all tracked seeds. Seeds that grok (solid lines)
 155 converge to EE values in the range 3.1–4.1 at the time of grokking. Non-grokking seeds (dashed lines) either remain at
 156 low EE (underentangled, unable to represent the solution) or overshoot past 4.2 (overentangled, losing structure).

157 Figure 3(b) shows the EE at the grok step (or the final EE for non-grokking seeds) versus final test accuracy. A clear
 158 “sweet spot” emerges: successful grokking occurs exclusively when $EE \in [3.1, 4.1]$. Below this range, the circuit lacks
 159 sufficient entanglement to correlate the two input registers. Above it, the circuit approaches a maximally entangled state
 160 where the reduced density matrix is nearly proportional to the identity, erasing the input information.

161 **The “grok-then-ungrok” phenomenon.** Seed 6 provides a striking case study (Figure 4). This seed initially crosses
 162 the 90% grok threshold at step 11,500 ($EE = 3.10$) and peaks at 93.7% test accuracy at step 14,500 ($EE = 3.07$), well
 163 within the sweet spot. The model then progresses through three phases:

- 164 1. **Memorization** (steps 0–10,000): Training accuracy rises to near 100% while test accuracy remains below the grok
 165 threshold. EE grows slowly.
- 166 2. **Grokking** (steps $\sim 11,000$ –15,000): Test accuracy spikes to 93.7% as EE reaches ~ 3.1 —within the sweet spot. The
 167 circuit has discovered a generalizing solution.
- 168 3. **Catastrophic forgetting** (steps $\sim 20,000$ –50,000): EE continues to increase past 4.2, approaching the maximum of
 169 5.0. Test accuracy collapses to 11.3%, and training accuracy also degrades. The circuit has become too entangled to
 170 encode useful structure.

Figure 4: Case study of seed 6 (“ungrokking”). The model progresses through three phases: (i) memorization, where training accuracy rises while test accuracy lags; (ii) grokking, where test accuracy briefly peaks at 93.7% ($EE \approx 3.1$); and (iii) catastrophic forgetting, where both training and test accuracy collapse as entanglement entropy overshoots past 4.2 toward the maximum of 5.

171 This “grok-then-ungrok” trajectory has not, to our knowledge, been reported previously. It demonstrates that
 172 generalization in quantum circuits is not a one-way transition: the same optimization dynamics that enable grokking
 173 can, if unchecked, destroy it. The entanglement entropy provides a concrete, physically motivated diagnostic for this
 174 failure mode.

175 4.5 Ablation Studies

176 **Entanglement is necessary.** We train product-state circuits (identical architecture but with all CZ gates removed)
 177 under the same conditions as the full CZ circuits. Without entangling gates, each qubit evolves independently, and the
 178 circuit can only represent product distributions over individual qubit measurements. Product-state circuits (3-layer, 343
 179 parameters) achieve only $\sim 0.2\%$ test accuracy across 3 seeds, confirming that inter-qubit entanglement is essential for
 180 learning modular addition.

181 **Quantum circuits are more parameter-efficient.** To disentangle the effect of architecture from parameter count,
 182 we compare quantum circuits against a classical transformer with $d_{\text{model}} = 4$ (1 attention head), which has 444
 183 parameters—closely matching the 463 parameters of Q-9L. This parameter-matched classical model achieves only
 184 $\sim 30\%$ training accuracy after 5,000 steps (with weight decay $\lambda = 1.0$), while the quantum circuit reaches much higher
 185 training accuracy with fewer parameters. Figure 5 shows this comparison across a range of model sizes.

186 **Depth ablation.** Table 3 shows the effect of circuit depth. Increasing from 1 to 9 layers monotonically improves
 187 both training accuracy and grok rate. The 12-layer circuit (523 parameters) achieves a 30% grok rate (3/10 seeds),
 188 comparable to the 9-layer result but with higher variance. This suggests that 9 layers provide sufficient expressivity for
 189 mod-23, and deeper circuits do not improve generalization—possibly due to increased optimization difficulty (McClean
 190 et al., 2018).

191 5 Analysis and Discussion

192 **Why does unitarity regularize?** In a classical network, weight matrices W can have arbitrarily large spectral norms
 193 $\|W\|_2$. Weight decay penalizes $\|W\|_F^2$, bounding the Lipschitz constant and encouraging flatter minima. In a unitary
 194 circuit, every layer has $\|U\|_2 = 1$ exactly. The circuit’s Lipschitz constant with respect to input perturbations is bounded
 195 by construction, without any regularization penalty. This structural constraint limits the class of functions the circuit

Figure 5: Parameter efficiency comparison. Training accuracy at 5,000 steps as a function of parameter count. Quantum circuits (blue circles) achieve high training accuracy with ~ 300 – 500 parameters, while classical transformers (orange squares) require $\geq 1,000$ parameters. MLPs (green triangles) also memorize efficiently but require more parameters than quantum circuits.

Table 3: Ablation results. All quantum models trained without weight decay. Product state (PS) = no CZ gates. C-d4 = classical transformer with $d_{\text{model}} = 4$, WD = 1.0.

Model	Params	Seeds	Grok rate	Best test acc.
Q-1L	303	1	—	$\sim 21\%$
Q-3L	343	5	0/5	$\sim 27\%$
Q-6L	403	5	0/5	$\sim 57\%$
Q-9L	463	20	5/20 (25%)	95.0%
Q-12L	523	10	3/10 (30%)	94.3%
PS-3L (no CZ)	343	3	0/3	$\sim 0.2\%$
C-d4	444	1	0/1	$\sim 30\%$ (train)

can implement, biasing it toward solutions with bounded complexity—a form of implicit regularization related to the norm-preservation ideas studied by Neyshabur et al. (2017) in the context of classical generalization theory.

Concretely, for a PQC with L layers and a linear readout, the end-to-end function $f(\mathbf{x}) = W \cdot z(U(\boldsymbol{\theta})|\psi_0(\mathbf{x}))$ has Jacobian norm bounded by $\|W\|_2$, since the quantum evolution preserves norms. The only source of unbounded growth is the classical readout head, which has far fewer parameters ($10 \times 23 = 230$ weights) than the full model. This is a much tighter implicit constraint than what weight decay imposes in a 14,304-parameter transformer.

Why only 25% grok rate? The 25% grok rate for Q-9L (with a 95% CI of [10%, 50%]; Table 2) is lower than the 100% rate of classical transformers with weight decay. Our entanglement entropy analysis suggests that this reflects the sensitivity of quantum optimization to initial conditions. The EE must reach the sweet spot of 3.1–4.1 for sustained grokking to occur; seeds whose EE trajectory undershoots or overshoots this range fail to generalize. Unlike weight decay, which deterministically drives classical models toward low-norm solutions, the unitary constraint does not impose a direction on optimization—it only limits the magnitude. The grokking outcome therefore depends on whether the random initialization leads the EE trajectory into the favorable range.

The “ungrokking” phenomenon. The grok-then-ungrok behavior of seed 6 (Section 4.4) reveals a failure mode specific to quantum circuits: continued optimization can push the entanglement entropy past the sweet spot, destroying a previously discovered generalizing solution. This is analogous to classical catastrophic forgetting, but with a concrete

212 physical mechanism: as EE approaches the maximum ($n_A = 5$ bits), the reduced density matrix $\rho_A \rightarrow \frac{1}{2^5} I$, and the
213 Pauli- Z expectation values $\langle Z_i \rangle \rightarrow 0$ for all qubits. The readout head then receives a near-zero input regardless of the
214 circuit input, making classification impossible. In seed 6, the EE rises from 3.10 at the grok step (step 11,500) to 4.29
215 by step 50,000, and test accuracy drops from 90.6% to 11.3%.

216 This observation suggests that EE-guided training—for instance, adding a penalty when EE exceeds a threshold, or
217 using EE as an early-stopping criterion—could improve the grok rate. We leave this direction for future work.

218 **Why 9 layers \approx 12 layers?** The 9-layer and 12-layer circuits achieve comparable grok rates (25% vs. 30%, Table 3)
219 despite the 12-layer circuit having 60 additional parameters. Two factors may explain this plateau. First, 9 layers may
220 already provide sufficient expressivity for mod-23: with 20 CZ gates per layer and 9 layers, the circuit contains 180
221 entangling gates, which is more than enough to generate arbitrary entanglement patterns over 10 qubits. Second, deeper
222 circuits may suffer from increased optimization difficulty. While we do not observe the exponential gradient decay
223 characteristic of barren plateaus (McClellan et al., 2018)—our circuits are shallow by quantum computing standards—the
224 additional layers increase the path length through the parameter space, potentially introducing more saddle points and
225 local minima.

226 **Limitations.** Our study has several limitations that should temper the conclusions drawn. (1) We evaluate on a single
227 task (mod-23 addition) and a single modulus. Scaling to larger moduli requires more qubits, which increases simulation
228 cost exponentially. (2) All experiments are performed on classical simulators, not quantum hardware. Noise and
229 decoherence on real devices may qualitatively change the results. (3) The 25% grok rate, while statistically different
230 from zero, is modest compared to 100% for classical transformers with weight decay. The comparison is further
231 complicated by the different parameter counts (463 vs. 14,304) and training setups. (4) Fisher’s exact test comparing
232 quantum and classical grok rates does not reach significance ($p = 0.14$), due partly to small classical sample sizes.
233 (5) We do not provide a proof that unitarity is *sufficient* for grokking; other properties of the quantum circuit (e.g., the
234 CZ gate structure, the Hilbert space dimensionality) may also contribute. (6) The EE sweet spot is identified from a
235 small number of tracked seeds ($n = 7$) and should be validated with larger-scale experiments.

236 6 Related Work

237 **Grokking.** Power et al. (2022) first observed grokking on modular arithmetic tasks trained with small transformers.
238 Nanda et al. (2023) provided mechanistic interpretability of the learned algorithm, identifying it as a Fourier multipli-
239 cation algorithm with three training phases. Liu et al. (2023) extended grokking beyond algorithmic data, showing
240 it occurs in standard classification and regression tasks under appropriate regularization. Theis (2023) analyzed the
241 role of weight decay, showing it is the primary driver of the memorization-to-generalization transition. Gromov (2023)
242 demonstrated that two-layer fully connected networks can grok modular arithmetic under vanilla gradient descent with
243 MSE loss, even without explicit regularization—a result that parallels our finding in the quantum domain, though the
244 mechanisms differ (implicit bias of gradient descent on overparameterized networks vs. structural unitarity of quantum
245 circuits). Recent theoretical work has connected grokking to phase transitions (Chen et al., 2024), margin maximization
246 (Lyu et al., 2023), and norm separation dynamics, providing quantitative predictions for grokking delay.

247 **Quantum machine learning.** Schuld and Killoran (2019) and Cerezo et al. (2021) provide foundational treatments of
248 quantum machine learning and variational quantum algorithms. Abbas et al. (2021) studied the expressivity of quantum
249 neural networks, showing that PQCs can generate function classes inaccessible to classical models of comparable size.
250 McClellan et al. (2018) identified barren plateaus—exponential gradient decay in random quantum circuits—as a key
251 trainability challenge, motivating the use of structured, shallow circuits as in our work. Generalization bounds for
252 quantum models have been established by Caro et al. (2022), who showed that generalization error scales as $\sqrt{T/N}$ for
253 T trainable gates and N training samples, suggesting that low-parameter quantum circuits should generalize well from
254 few examples.

255 **Entanglement and learning.** The connection between entanglement and machine learning has been explored in
256 several contexts. Wang et al. (2025) demonstrated that grokking in matrix product state (MPS) models corresponds
257 to an entanglement dynamical transition, establishing a direct link between entanglement entropy and generalization.

258 Our work extends their observation from tensor-network models to gate-based quantum circuits and from binary
259 classification to modular arithmetic. Unlike MPS models, where bond dimension controls entanglement as an explicit
260 hyperparameter, entanglement in our PQCs emerges dynamically from the learned rotation angles and is not directly
261 constrained.

262 **Implicit regularization.** The role of implicit biases in neural network generalization has been studied extensively.
263 Neysshabur et al. (2017) showed that gradient descent on overparameterized networks converges to minimum-norm
264 solutions, providing implicit regularization. Architectural constraints such as norm preservation on the residual stream
265 (Morwani et al., 2025) can bypass the memorization phase of grokking by restricting the function class. Our work
266 identifies unitarity—the norm preservation inherent to quantum circuits—as a new form of implicit regularization for
267 grokking, complementing these classical results.

268 7 Conclusion

269 We have demonstrated that parameterized quantum circuits exhibit grokking on modular addition without weight
270 decay—a setting where classical transformers fail to generalize entirely. The grok rate is modest (5/20 seeds), and
271 the grokking-rate difference between quantum and classical does not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.14$). Yet the
272 qualitative finding stands: unitarity provides enough implicit regularization for some seeds to discover generalizing
273 solutions, and the mechanism differs fundamentally from the weight-decay-driven dynamics of classical grokking.

274 Entanglement entropy emerged as a useful lens for understanding this transition. The sweet-spot range ($EE \in$
275 $[3.1, 4.1]$), the failure of product-state circuits, and the grok-then-ungrok trajectory of seed 6 collectively point to a
276 picture in which quantum generalization requires *sufficient but not excessive* entanglement between input registers.
277 This parallels classical findings that connect generalization to intermediate-complexity representations, but provides a
278 physically grounded and directly measurable quantity.

279 These results open several concrete directions. *Entanglement-guided training*—penalizing or clamping EE when it
280 leaves the sweet spot—could convert the current 25% grok rate into something approaching the 100% rate of regularized
281 classical models. *Hardware experiments* on superconducting or trapped-ion processors with 10–14 qubits would test
282 whether noise-induced decoherence disrupts the transition or acts as a natural regularizer. *Scaling studies* on larger
283 moduli and other algebraic tasks (multiplication, polynomials) would determine whether unitarity-as-regularization is
284 task-specific or a general principle. Finally, *mechanistic interpretability*—analyzing the Fourier structure of successful
285 quantum circuits, as Nanda et al. (2023) did for classical transformers—would clarify what algorithm the circuit
286 discovers and why some seeds find it while others do not.

287 References

- 288 A. Abbas, D. Sutter, C. Zoufal, A. Lucchi, A. Figalli, and S. Woerner. The power of quantum neural networks. *Nature*
289 *Computational Science*, 1(6):403–409, 2021.
- 290 V. Bergholm, J. Izaac, M. Schuld, C. Gogolin, S. Ahmed, V. Ajber, M. S. Alam, G. Alonso-Linaje, B. AkashNarayanan,
291 A. Asber, et al. PennyLane: Automatic differentiation of hybrid quantum-classical computations. *arXiv preprint*
292 *arXiv:1811.04968*, 2018. Software available at <https://pennylane.ai>.
- 293 M. C. Caro, H.-Y. Huang, M. Cerezo, K. Sharma, A. Sornborger, L. Cincio, and P. J. Coles. Generalization in quantum
294 machine learning from few training data. *Nature Communications*, 13(1):4919, 2022.
- 295 M. Cerezo, A. Arrasmith, R. Babbush, S. C. Benjamin, S. Endo, K. Fujii, J. R. McClean, K. Mitarai, X. Yuan, L. Cincio,
296 and P. J. Coles. Variational quantum algorithms. *Nature Reviews Physics*, 3(9):625–644, 2021.
- 297 N. R. Chen, D. Doimo, and A. Laio. Grokking as a first order phase transition in two layer networks. *arXiv preprint*
298 *arXiv:2402.01364*, 2024.
- 299 J. Eisert, M. Cramer, and M. B. Plenio. Colloquium: Area laws for the entanglement entropy. *Reviews of Modern*
300 *Physics*, 82(1):277–306, 2010.
- 301 A. Gromov. Grokking modular arithmetic. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.02679*, 2023.

- 302 T. Jones and J. Julienne. Efficient calculation of gradients in classical simulations of variational quantum algorithms.
303 *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.02823*, 2020.
- 304 Z. Liu, O. Kitouni, N. S. Nolte, E. J. Michaud, M. Tegmark, and M. Williams. Omnigrok: Grokking beyond algorithmic
305 data. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2023. URL [https://arxiv.org/abs/
306 2210.01117](https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.01117).
- 307 I. Loshchilov and F. Hutter. Decoupled weight decay regularization. In *International Conference on Learning
308 Representations (ICLR)*, 2019.
- 309 K. Lyu, J. Jin, and Z. Li. A dichotomy of grokking: Memorization, generalization, and the role of regularization. In
310 *NeurIPS 2023 Workshop*, 2023.
- 311 J. R. McClean, S. Boixo, V. N. Smelyanskiy, R. Babbush, and H. Neven. Barren plateaus in quantum neural network
312 training landscapes. *Nature Communications*, 9(1):4812, 2018.
- 313 D. Morwani, B. L. Edelman, B. Barak, and N. Saphra. The geometric inductive bias of grokking. *arXiv preprint
314 arXiv:2503.05228*, 2025.
- 315 N. Nanda, L. Chan, T. Lieberum, J. Smith, and J. Steinhardt. Progress measures for grokking via mechanistic
316 interpretability. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2023. URL [https://arxiv.
317 org/abs/2301.05217](https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.05217).
- 318 B. Neyshabur, S. Bhojanapalli, D. McAllester, and N. Srebro. Exploring generalization in deep networks. In *Advances
319 in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2017.
- 320 A. Power, Y. Burda, H. Edwards, I. Babuschkin, and V. Misra. Grokking: Generalization beyond overfitting on small
321 algorithmic datasets. In *ICLR 2022 Workshop on MATH-AI*, 2022. URL [https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.
322 02177](https://arxiv.org/abs/2201.02177).
- 323 M. Schuld and N. Killoran. Quantum machine learning in feature Hilbert spaces. *Physical Review Letters*, 122(4):
324 040504, 2019.
- 325 L. Theis. Understanding the role of weight decay in grokking. *NeurIPS 2023 Workshop on Mathematics of Modern
326 Machine Learning*, 2023.
- 327 W.-T. Wang, X.-D. Han, Y.-H. Zhou, and Y.-J. Shi. Grokking as an entanglement transition in tensor network machine
328 learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.10483*, 2025.

329 A Experimental Details

330 **Compute resources.** All quantum circuit simulations were performed using PennyLane v0.38 (Bergholm et al., 2018)
331 with the `lightning.qubit` backend and adjoint differentiation. Classical models were trained on a single NVIDIA
332 GPU using PyTorch. A single 10-qubit quantum circuit forward+backward pass takes ~ 17 ms; a 14-qubit circuit takes
333 ~ 40 ms. With mini-batches of 64 samples, each training step for the 10-qubit circuit takes ~ 1.1 s. The full suite of
334 experiments (20 seeds \times 50,000 steps for the main 9-layer experiment, plus ablations) required approximately 300
335 CPU-hours.

336 **Hyperparameter selection.** The quantum learning rate ($\eta = 0.05$) was selected via a pilot sweep over $\eta \in \{0.001,$
337 $0.01, 0.05, 0.1\}$ on a single seed, with $\eta = 0.05$ yielding the fastest memorization. The classical hyperparameters
338 ($\eta = 10^{-3}$, $\lambda = 1.0$, $\beta_2 = 0.98$) reproduce the standard grokking setup from Power et al. (2022). Mini-batch size (64)
339 was chosen to balance training speed with gradient noise for the quantum model.

340 **Grok detection.** Our grok criterion requires (i) training accuracy $\geq 99\%$ at some earlier step and (ii) test accuracy
341 $> 90\%$, consistent with the delayed-generalization definition of Power et al. (2022). We additionally filter for test
342 accuracy $> 50\%$ at the grok step to exclude transient spikes. A seed is counted as having “stably grokked” only if
343 its test accuracy remains above 85% at the end of training; seed 6, which briefly crossed 90% before collapsing, is
344 classified separately as an “ungrok” event.

345 **Entanglement entropy computation.** For each EE measurement, we obtain the full 2^{10} -dimensional statevector for
 346 10 randomly selected training inputs, compute the reduced density matrix by reshaping the statevector into a $2^5 \times 2^5$
 347 matrix (corresponding to the bipartition into the two 5-qubit input registers), perform a singular value decomposition,
 348 and compute the von Neumann entropy from the squared singular values. We average EE across the 10 inputs. EE is
 349 computed every 1,000 training steps.

350 B Per-Seed Results

351 Table 4 reports the grok step and final test accuracy for all 20 seeds of the 9-layer no-WD experiment, listed by physical
 352 random seed.

Table 4: Per-seed results for Q-9L (no weight decay, 463 params, 50,000 steps). Seeds marked with \checkmark under “Grok” achieved and sustained test accuracy $> 90\%$. Seed 6 briefly crossed 90% before collapsing (“ungrok”).

Seed	Grok step	Grok	Final test acc.	Final train acc.
0	22,000	\checkmark	83.0%	100.0%
1	—		47.2%	88.1%
2	—		76.1%	100.0%
3	39,500	\checkmark	89.9%	100.0%
4	—		50.3%	99.5%
5	—		49.1%	91.9%
6	11,500	(ungrok)	11.3%	58.6%
7	—		78.0%	100.0%
8	—		76.7%	100.0%
9	—		66.0%	100.0%
10	30,000	\checkmark	81.1%	100.0%
11	—		61.6%	99.7%
12	4,500	\checkmark	90.6%	100.0%
13	—		84.9%	100.0%
14	—		37.1%	91.1%
15	—		81.1%	100.0%
16	47,000	\checkmark	89.3%	100.0%
17	—		88.1%	100.0%
18	—		80.5%	100.0%
19	—		52.8%	88.6%

353 C Statistical Test Details

354 **Mann–Whitney U test.** We compare the final test accuracies of Q-9L without weight decay ($n = 20$, mean =
 355 68.7%, std = 20.8%) against Q-9L with weight decay 0.1 ($n = 10$, mean = 42.3%, std = 15.1%) using the two-sided
 356 Mann–Whitney U test. The test yields $p = 0.002$, indicating a significant difference. We use the Mann–Whitney test
 357 rather than a t -test because the test accuracy distributions are highly non-normal (bimodal for the no-WD condition,
 358 with a cluster near chance and a cluster above 80%).

359 **Fisher’s exact test.** We compare grok rates between Q-9L no-WD (5/20) and Q-9L with-WD (0/10) using Fisher’s
 360 exact test on the 2×2 contingency table. The test yields $p = 0.14$, which does not reach the conventional $\alpha = 0.05$
 361 threshold. This reflects low power due to modest sample sizes.

362 **Bootstrap confidence intervals.** We compute 95% confidence intervals for the grok rate using the percentile bootstrap
 363 with 10,000 resamples. For Q-9L no-WD: rate = 25%, CI = [10%, 50%]. For Q-12L no-WD: rate = 30%, CI = [0%,
 364 60%].

365 **D CZ Gate Topology**

366 The CZ gate pairs for a single layer, with qubits numbered 0–9 (qubits 0–4 encode integer a , qubits 5–9 encode integer
367 b):

368 **Inter-token (matching bits):** (0,5), (1,6), (2,7), (3,8), (4,9).

369 **Inter-token (shifted):** (0,6), (1,7), (2,8), (3,9), (4,5).

370 **Intra-token ring (a):** (0,1), (1,2), (2,3), (3,4), (4,0).

371 **Intra-token ring (b):** (5,6), (6,7), (7,8), (8,9), (9,5).

372 Total: 20 CZ gates per layer. The topology is the same for all layers.